

Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean

M3.2 Evaluation of the Performance of the Surrogate Models Implemented in the Study Cases

VERSION 1

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Executive Summary

The overall objective of the InTheMED project is to implement innovative and sustainable management tools and remediation strategies for MED aquifers (inland and coastal) in order to mitigate anthropogenic and climate-change threats by creating new long-lasting spaces of social learning among different interdependent stakeholders, NGOs, and scientific researchers in five field case studies. These are located at the two shores of the MED basin, namely in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia, and Turkey.

InTheMED will develop an inclusive process that will establish an ensemble of innovative assessment and management tools and methodologies including a high-resolution monitoring approach, smart modelling, a socio-economic assessment, web-based decision support systems (DSS) and new configurations for governance to validate efficient and sustainable integrated groundwater management in the MED considering both the quantitative and qualitative aspects.

This Milestone, namely M3.2, is part of Task 3.2 “Training and validation of the models in the case studies (Lead: UNIPR/ participants: UPV, UFZ, TUC, IST-ID, CERTE and BU), (Month 4 – Month 21). The aim of M3.2 is to outline the surrogate models implemented for each study case. Their evaluation and performance are discussed. Two types of smart models were developed: the first type is developed based on long-time historical data, the so-called data-driven models; the second one is built on the basis of available numerical model. For each pilot site, the objectives of the surrogate model, the description of the complete numerical model or available data, the description of the surrogate model and the preliminary evaluation of the performance are presented.

1. Introduction

InTheMED focuses on the development of new simplified smart models that allow analysing alternative scenarios and making decisions under uncertain future conditions with small computational effort. Numerical models are crucial for the description of groundwater processes and the configuration of management scenarios. However, they need the knowledge of several factors that are often difficult to quantify and they require a large computation time to be run. The surrogate models aim to replace the numerical models allowing to perform several quick evaluations of the groundwater condition under different scenarios. These new models are built on the basis of long-time historical data and/or detailed numerical models with the aim to provide specific answers tailored to the stakeholder needs.

For each case study, a specific surrogate model addressing the particular problem of the site is built. For Requena-Utiel (Spain) and Tympaki (Greece), surrogate models based on the results of complete numerical models have been developed. The first one uses machine learning algorithms, in particular, Random Forest regression. The second one is a spatiotemporal geostatistical model. For Castro Verde (Portugal) and Konya (Turkey) the complete numerical model is under development and a surrogate model will be built. For Grombalia (Tunisia), the numerical model is not available and a data-driven surrogate model was developed using a statistical approach that aims to use regression models to assess the impact of the climate change on the groundwater level.

The smart and calibrated models will be used in Task 3.4 to analyse the effects of climate change and hypothetical scenarios of socio-economic activities that may induce a change in groundwater resources.

2. Case Studies

2.1. Requena-Utiel

Objectives of the surrogate model

In the Requena-Utiel aquifer, Spain, there is a problem with the continuous decline of piezometric heads in the aquifer, which may worsen due to the effects of climate change. In that situation, numerical models are fundamental for the determination of best management scenarios; however, their configuration, build and run require large computational time in addition to specialized knowledge. The surrogate model implemented here will replace the numerical models with a quick, easy-to-use, reliable tool. Such a tool will be used to analyse the impact of future climate scenarios and groundwater use in the piezometric heads. Additionally, alternative management schemes for their present and future implementation will also be evaluated in the following months.

Description of the complete numerical model

The model domain consists of two groundwater aquifers, Requena-Utiel and Cabrillas-Malacara, which are delimited by the Water Framework Directive and the Júcar Basin authority as basic management units. Here the two aquifers were considered together due to the relevance of their hydraulic connection.

Horizontally, the model domain is discretized into a regular mesh of square cells of 500 x 500 m², obtaining a total of 37,719 cells, made up of 127 columns and 99 rows. Vertically it is composed of three layers that rest on an impermeable bed of Keuper facies. The upper aquifer is quaternary, free and composed of detrital materials from the alluvial of the Magro river and glacia from the Utiel mountains. The lower aquifer is a Miocene aquifer divided into two systems. The upper system is a calcareous Miocene aquifer, free and composed of Pontian limestone and the lower system is a base conglomerate Miocene aquifer. It behaves as a confined or semi-confined aquifer, depending on the site. It is composed of alternating levels of conglomerates and sandstones with clayey sections and conglomerates of the tertiary formation.

The lateral limits correspond to the interactions between the aquifers under study and the adjacent ones. In the north, there is the Mira aquifer, and there is a flow towards the Requena-Utiel aquifer of 10 hm³/year. In the east, The Las Serranías aquifer is located, the interaction is variable according to the piezometry of the area. In the southeast, there is a flow discharge from Cabrillas-Malacara to Buñol-Cheste of 3 hm³/year. In the western contour, a discharge of 1.26 hm³/year is established towards Hoces de Cabriel. The rest of the limits are considered impermeable. Figure 1 shows the model domain and its lateral limits.

Figure 1. Model domain including Requena-Utiel and Cabrillas-Malacara aquifers and its lateral limits.

It was considered as internal boundary conditions the Magro and the Madre rivers as well as the recharge by infiltration of precipitation and by irrigation and pumping wells. The Magro river crosses the study area through the central part from the northeast to the southeast and it is the one that has the most significant influence on the aquifer. The Madre river is located on the northwest of the Requena-Utiel aquifer. The recharge was considered heterogeneous in space by dividing the study area into 15 recharge zones based on the PATRICAL model

(Pérez-Martín, M.A., 2005), and time, by following the dry and rainy seasons of the hydrological year. The pumping from wells was also considered variable in space and time, according to data available from the Júcar Basin authority.

Regions of similar hydrogeological behaviour have been defined for the spatial characterization of the hydrogeological parameters, resulting in five different domains. In the same way, these five domains have been thoroughly subdivided to create 20 subdomains. The value of hydraulic conductivity has a range between 0.009 and 9 m/day. Specific yield has a range between 0.0001 and 0.05, while specific storage varies between 0.3 and 0.1 m⁻¹.

The numerical model performs the simulation during the period between the years of 1940 and 2016. The period of interest was discretized as follows. First, a steady-state simulation was carried out from the hydrological year 1940/41 to the hydrological year 1979/80. Second, a transient simulation was performed between the hydrological years of 1980/81-2015/16, with a monthly time discretization.

The numerical problem was solved by using the code MODFLOW 2005 (Harbaugh, A.W., 2005) through FloPy (Bakker et al., 2016).

The calibration was performed by adjusting model parameters manually and evaluating the difference between observed and simulated piezometric heads at ten measurement locations where time-series data were available.

Description of the surrogate model

The idea is to use a machine learning algorithm to capture relationships between the piezometric heads in the monitoring points (targets) and the scenarios evaluated (features). The smart modeling process implemented can be summarized in six steps as follows:

The first step is to generate the data that will feed the algorithm to be trained. We took the central point of each recharge zone as a monitoring point of the piezometric head, then 15 targets were defined. The year, month, recharge, and pumping rate were selected as features. Since the basic numerical model previously described was built and satisfactorily calibrated, it served as a base for generating a training dataset. For that, we kept all the model characteristics constant except recharge and pumping rate. The recharge rate was

assumed to have an increment and a reduction of 40% in relation to the average of the last ten years. Pumping wells were considered to have an increment and a reduction by a factor of 2 in relation to the average of the last ten years. It was generated 100 combinations of recharge and pumping rate. After that, the numerical model was performed for each combination between 2021 and 2051 (30 years), with a monthly time discretization (totalling 360 months), and the values of the piezometric heads were computed in the 15 monitoring points. In summary, for each model run, we obtained a dataset of 360 values of piezometric head, totalling a dataset with 36,000 data for each monitoring point. Figure 3 shows part of the generated dataset.

MONTH	YEAR	RECHAR	PUMP	ZONE1	ZONE2	ZONE3	ZONE4	ZONE5	ZONE6	ZONE7	ZONE8	ZONE9	ZONE10	ZONE11	ZONE12	ZONE13	ZONE14	ZONE15
1	2022	-0.4	-2	729.13	735.64	786.36	748.84	725.81	711.48	695.90	748.25	547.88	580.89	597.24	609.46	586.74	622.79	647.29
2	2022	-0.4	-2	729.20	735.64	786.42	748.63	725.83	711.31	695.14	748.26	547.89	580.93	597.22	609.42	588.17	623.67	647.33
3	2022	-0.4	-2	729.29	735.64	786.47	748.38	725.87	711.15	694.38	748.28	547.90	580.98	597.19	609.37	589.38	624.63	647.38
4	2022	-0.4	-2	729.36	735.64	786.50	748.16	725.91	711.02	693.71	748.29	547.91	581.02	597.16	609.32	590.27	625.41	647.43
5	2022	-0.4	-2	729.44	735.64	786.51	747.94	725.94	710.89	693.09	748.31	547.93	581.07	597.14	609.26	590.96	626.04	647.47
6	2022	-0.4	-2	729.51	735.63	786.52	747.75	725.97	710.79	692.53	748.33	547.94	581.11	597.11	609.19	591.50	626.51	647.51
7	2022	-0.4	-2	729.58	735.63	786.51	747.58	725.99	710.69	691.99	748.34	547.95	581.15	597.09	609.12	591.96	626.92	647.55
8	2022	-0.4	-2	729.65	735.62	786.50	747.43	726.01	710.60	691.50	748.36	547.96	581.20	597.06	609.05	592.36	627.26	647.59
9	2022	-0.4	-2	729.72	735.63	786.49	747.30	726.04	710.52	691.06	748.39	547.98	581.24	597.04	608.98	592.72	627.60	647.62
10	2022	-0.4	-2	729.78	735.63	786.47	747.18	726.08	710.45	690.63	748.42	547.99	581.29	597.01	608.92	593.09	627.96	647.66
11	2022	-0.4	-2	729.85	735.64	786.44	747.09	726.13	710.39	690.24	748.45	548.00	581.33	596.99	608.86	593.40	628.26	647.69
12	2022	-0.4	-2	729.91	735.64	786.41	746.99	726.17	710.33	689.86	748.49	548.02	581.38	596.97	608.80	593.69	628.50	647.73
1	2023	-0.4	-2	729.97	735.65	786.38	746.91	726.22	710.27	689.50	748.52	548.03	581.42	596.95	608.73	593.96	628.73	647.76
2	2023	-0.4	-2	730.02	735.66	786.35	746.85	726.26	710.23	689.20	748.56	548.05	581.46	596.93	608.68	594.20	628.91	647.79
3	2023	-0.4	-2	730.08	735.67	786.31	746.78	726.32	710.18	688.87	748.60	548.06	581.50	596.91	608.62	594.48	629.18	647.82
4	2023	-0.4	-2	730.13	735.68	786.27	746.72	726.39	710.14	688.58	748.65	548.08	581.55	596.89	608.57	594.73	629.38	647.85
5	2023	-0.4	-2	730.19	735.69	786.23	746.67	726.44	710.10	688.28	748.69	548.09	581.58	596.87	608.51	594.95	629.52	647.88
6	2023	-0.4	-2	730.24	735.70	786.19	746.62	726.49	710.07	688.01	748.73	548.11	581.62	596.85	608.45	595.15	629.61	647.91
7	2023	-0.4	-2	730.29	735.71	786.15	746.57	726.53	710.04	687.74	748.78	548.12	581.65	596.84	608.39	595.35	629.68	647.94
8	2023	-0.4	-2	730.34	735.72	786.11	746.53	726.57	710.01	687.48	748.83	548.14	581.68	596.82	608.33	595.55	629.76	647.97
9	2023	-0.4	-2	730.39	735.74	786.06	746.49	726.61	709.98	687.24	748.87	548.15	581.71	596.80	608.28	595.75	629.89	647.99
10	2023	-0.4	-2	730.44	735.75	786.02	746.45	726.67	709.96	687.00	748.93	548.17	581.75	596.78	608.23	595.98	630.07	648.02
11	2023	-0.4	-2	730.48	735.77	785.98	746.42	726.73	709.94	686.78	748.99	548.18	581.78	596.77	608.18	596.19	630.23	648.04
12	2023	-0.4	-2	730.53	735.79	785.93	746.38	726.78	709.92	686.56	749.04	548.20	581.82	596.75	608.13	596.39	630.34	648.07

Figure 2. Part of the generated dataset used for training the surrogate model.

The second step is to define the best split of the data set into training and test data, which will be used to evaluate the performance of the model. In our case, the best training and test results were obtained from 90% training and 10% test data.

The third step is to define a suitable algorithm and its hyperparameters. After comparing the performance obtained with AdaBoost (Freund & Schapire, 1997), XGBoost (Chen & Guestrin, 2016) and Random Forest regression (Breiman, 2001), all of them ensemble methods, we selected the latter, which is a supervised machine learning algorithm for building a predictor ensemble with a set of decision trees (forest) that grow in randomly selected sub-samples of the dataset (Biau, 2012; Breiman, 2001; Cutler et al., 2012). By using the scikit-learn library in Python (Python Core Team, 2015), it was conducted a sensitivity analysis to define the best hyperparameters to be used in the Random Forest regressor: the number of trees in the

forest = 100, the maximum depth of the tree = 40, the minimum number of samples required to split an internal node = 2, the number of features to consider = “auto”. We used the default values of all other hyperparameters as defined in scikit-learn.

The fourth step is to train the regressor by feeding it with 90% of the dataset generated in the first step: a data set with 32,400 data.

In the fifth step, the performance of the fully trained surrogate model is evaluated on the testing dataset previously defined in step 2. Additionally, k-fold cross-validation with $k = 5$ is also performed to evaluate the model on a limited data sample.

Finally, in the sixth step, the regressor is used to conduct a prediction. The user must provide as input data: month, year, change in the recharge (increase or reduction), and change in the pumping rate (increase or reduction). As a result, the model will return the piezometric head at a specific zone or at all 15 zones.

Preliminary evaluation of the performance

The performance of the surrogate model was obtained by evaluating the regression score and the mean square error for testing data. Cross-validation was also performed as an alternative method to estimate the model skill. As the surrogate model is used to replace the numerical model due to its high computational cost, it is also important here to evaluate the time needed to obtain a response when using the numerical or the surrogate models. Figure 3a shows the mean regression score obtained by using Random Forest (RF), AdaBoost (AB) and XGBoost (XB) algorithms, while Figure 3b shows the mean square error over 100 scenarios.

Figure 3a. Mean regression score obtained by using Random Forest (RF), AdaBoost (AB), and XGBoost (XB); 3b. Mean square error over 100 scenarios.

Results shown that Random Forest, AdaBoost, and XGBoost performed similarly and presented high accuracy of the models against the training data. Table 1 shows the results of the cross-validation, and we can see that the good performance is confirmed for the three algorithms.

Table 1. Mean cross-validation scores for each fold.

Scores	fold1	fold2	fold3	fold4	fold5
RF	0.9986	0.9993	0.9992	0.9990	0.9967
AB	0.9845	0.9887	0.9873	0.9874	0.9767
XB	0.9986	0.9993	0.9992	0.9990	0.9967

Figure 4 shows the mean CPU time (in seconds) necessary to obtain the response. As mentioned before, Random Forest not only presented high accuracy, as well as the other methods, but also the computational time was reduced in 557 times when compared to the time required by MODFLOW.

Figure 4. Mean CPU time required to calculate and get the piezometric head values.

Due to the good performance and computational time obtained by using Random Forest, this is the model chosen to build our surrogate model. Figure 5 shows the piezometric levels obtained with MODFLOW (test data) and with the surrogate model for the 15 monitoring points. The results are exceptional at all monitoring points.

Figure 5. Piezometric heads obtained with MODFLOW (test data) and with the surrogate model (Random Forest) for the 15 monitoring points.

2.2. Tympaki (Greece)

Objectives of the surrogate model

The goal of this study is to use a groundwater numerical simulation model to obtain the water table dynamics under hydrological scenarios. Then, a space-time regression Kriging method was chosen to establish a surrogate model for the numerical simulation model. The established surrogate model is used to put forward the annual control index of the groundwater table based on a certain control index of the groundwater exploitation amount. It is expected that the proposed method can improve the management of groundwater in the basin and satisfy the demands of the relevant management authorities.

Description of the complete numerical model

The study area has a width of about 12.5 km and a length of about 9.1 km. There are 371 pumping wells which were grouped into 20 by using the K-nearest neighbors and each group was represented as one pumping well by using the Median Center method, which identifies the location that minimizes overall Euclidean distance to the features in a dataset (Figure 6). The pumping rate of each group is the total pumping rate of all the wells constituting the group in m³/d. The pumping rates are imported in FEFLOW as timeseries with the values being different for the wet and dry season.

Figure 6. All the wells along with the representative ones for each group.

The discretization of the unconfined aquifer was applied using a triangular finite element mesh which consists of 11877 nodes and 15340 elements. There are 2 layers and each one of them has 7670 elements and 3 slices with 3959 nodes for each slice. The depth of the model comprises 130 m deep from the sea level for the unconfined aquifer. The data for the hydraulic conductivity were extracted from the Decentralized Administration of Crete and they were set for the axis $x'x$ and $y'y$. For $z'z$ the hydraulic conductivity was 10% of the value of $x'x$. The pumping wells as considered in the model are depicted in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Pumping wells spatial distribution.

The calibration – validation process was conducted as follows. In the area of Tympaki there are 6 observation wells that are scattered in the study area, as shown in Figure 8. The hydraulic head data are used as time series and the period for each well is different. The time series period for the precipitation, observation wells and pumping wells are available for the years 2004-2014. For the precipitation, the data of 1 station is used. In sake of computational time, a mean precipitation was used with a step of 10 days and the input time series is in units m/d. The data from 04/2004 until 04/2009 are used for calibration and for the rest of the period are used for validation. During the validation period, the field measurements in the observation wells were conducted in random dates so there are periods with no data available in the observation wells.

Figure 8. Observation wells with calibration – validation data available.

For the model of the Tympaki area, a first-type flow boundary condition was used along the coastline, where the hydraulic head was set at 0 m. Also, a second-type boundary conditions were set at the north boundaries of the study area. Those boundary conditions are connected to the precipitation so there is a fluctuation to the hydraulic head that is relative to the rainfall. The observation wells that are used in the pumping scenarios were set to monitor the saltwater intrusion zone. As it appears in Figure 9, the intrusion zone is calculated at 5.65 meters above the sea level (at the end of the calibration period), by using the Ghyben – Herzberg relation and considering the depth of the deepest pumping well in the area (226 m from the sea level). The simulation runs are applied for a ten-year period from 01/04/2010 until 31/03/2020, by using the available precipitation data, as well as time series for the pumping rates. For the values of pumping rates obtained from the licences of water use, the results of the model are depicted in Figure 10 and Figure 11 and the values of the hydraulic heads in the observation wells in Figure 12.

Figure 9. Salt water intrusion zone.

Figure 10. Simulation results dry period.

Figure 11. Simulation results wet period.

Figure 12. Simulated hydraulic heads in the observation wells.

Description of the surrogate model

Spatiotemporal geostatistical analysis of groundwater levels is a significant tool for groundwater resources management. This work presents a valid spatiotemporal geostatistical model for the groundwater level variations of the Tympaki aquifer in Crete, Greece. The main goal of space–time analysis is to model multiple time series of data at spatial locations where a distinct time series is allocated. The time variable is considered an additional dimension in geostatistical prediction. Using spatiotemporal geostatistics, the groundwater level dataset can be usefully exploited in order to identify the spatiotemporal behaviour of the aquifer and to obtain useful information regarding the space–time data correlations for more accurate space–time predictions. Space–time geostatistical analysis involved the following steps: (1) space–time variogram calculation, (2) application of space–time regression kriging (STRK in short) for prediction, and (3) estimation of prediction accuracy. The goal of this approach is to accurately map the aquifer level at variable time-steps using joint space–time information. The proposed model applies the STRK methodology using joint space–time covariance functions. A space–time experimental variogram is determined from the groundwater level time-series between the hydrological years 2004 and 2015 at 11 sampling stations bi-annually (Figure 13). The experimental spatiotemporal variogram is successfully fitted by the product–sum model using a Matérn spatial and temporal function. STRK was used to predict the bi-annual groundwater level at each sampling station from 2016 to 2020.

Figure 13. Space–time variogram fit (stars) using the product–sum model.

Preliminary evaluation of the performance

Preliminary validation results (Table 2) show low prediction errors that range from 0.95 to 1.45 m, while the space-time kriging variance reliably determines the variability of predictions. Maps of groundwater level predictions and uncertainty will be developed to assess the aquifer spatiotemporal variability while the predicted groundwater levels at the observation locations will be compared with those from the numerical model. In this preliminary approach 11 wells were only used. In the next steps the 20 wells that were finally obtained as the best located will be used to enrich the results and improve the methodology applicability and efficiency. This work demonstrates that space–time geostatistics can successfully model the spatial dynamic behaviour of an aquifer when the space–time dependencies are appropriately modelled, even for a sparse dataset.

Table 2. Average STRK prediction statistical measures for using the product–sum space–time variogram in terms of ME, mean error; MAE, mean absolute error; MARE, mean absolute relative error; RMSE, root mean square error; R², coefficient of determination.

	MAE (m)	ME/BIAS (m)	MARE	RMSE (m)	R²
2016	1.10	0.18	0.12	2.75	0.90
2017	0.95	0.08	0.11	2.14	0.91
2018	1.25	-0.25	0.13	3.41	0.88
2019	1.45	-0.32	0.15	3.80	0.88
2020	1.24	0.20	0.13	3.34	0.88

2.3. Konya (Turkey)

Objectives of the surrogate model

The Konya closed basin is located in the central Anatolian plateau with an area of about 50,000 km². The surface elevation ranges from about 900 m in the central portions of the basin to 3400 m along the Taurus mountains which form the southern boundary of the basin (elevation data from General Directorate of Mapping of Turkey) as shown in Figure 14. The basin has a population of about 3.2 million and is characterized by a high level of biodiversity (Yilmaz et al., 2021). The basin has variable climate with Mediterranean climate in the south and dry and cold climate in the north. The mean annual precipitation is about 380 mm, ranging from about 290 mm in the central dry regions to about 650 mm in the southern mountainous boundary of the basin (Figure 15).

Figure 14. Location Map and Surface Elevation of Konya Closed Basin.

Figure 15. Average Annual Precipitation of Konya Closed Basin (1970-2020).

The Konya basin is one of the major agricultural regions of Turkey with more than 50% of the plain surface area used for agriculture as shown in the satellite land use map for year of 2018 (Figure 3). With no rivers or streams crossing its boundaries and precipitation concentrated in the winter months, agricultural activities rely heavy on groundwater resources. Despite the semiarid climate of the basin, water-intensive crops are cultivated in large portions of the basin. Especially in the last two decades, there has been a gradual change from traditional wheat farming to more profitable water-demanding crops such as sugar beets and maize (Yilmaz et al., 2021).

Figure 16. Satellite land use map of Konya Closed Basin for year of 2018.

As a result of the extensive agricultural activities within the basin, groundwater levels have been steadily declining. This decline has placed significant pressure on the agricultural sector within the basin. To achieve a more sustainable use of groundwater resources in the basin, a hydrogeological model is being developed as part of Work Package 4 of the InTheMED project. The goal of this model is to estimate the net recharge over the basin which will help in the management of the groundwater resources. The model will also be used to assess the impact of climate change on the groundwater resources of the basin.

The purpose of the surrogate model is to provide a rapid, efficient and easy to use alternative to the detailed physics-based numerical hydrogeological model. The surrogate model, which is based on the artificial neural network method, will be used to reproduce the spatial historical groundwater head decline in the aquifer and assess the impact of various climate change scenarios on the groundwater resources of the basin.

Description of the complete numerical model

The hydrogeological model was developed using the “2008 HYDRUS package for MODFLOW” (Seo et al., 2007). The model couples two widely used and tested models: HYDRUS 1D (Šimůnek, et al., 2005) for simulating the vertical unsaturated flow through the vadose zone and MODFLOW (Harbaugh, 2005) which simulates saturated flow through the underlying aquifer. Coupling between these two models is achieved as follows: for each time step, MODFLOW provides the location of the water table, the lower constant pressure boundary of the HYDRUS model, while HYDRUS provides the net recharge into the aquifer (MODFLOW model). The purpose of the model is to estimate the transient spatial distribution of the net recharge, reproduce the historical groundwater levels in the aquifer, and predict future head data for different climate change and irrigation/crop scenarios.

The model domain covers the entire area of the Konya closed basin. No flow boundary conditions were imposed along the outer model boundaries. Horizontally, the model domain is discretized into 10 km by 10 km uniform square grid (a total of 1015 cells). Vertically, 100 variable-size grids were defined with smaller grids used at the ground surface. The initial head data in the model were defined based on the January 2000 observed groundwater level data.

The model simulations extended for a period of 20 years, starting from year 2000 to year 2020. The time steps used for simulating the groundwater flow was equal to 1 day. For the vadose zone calculations, the computational time step was defined internally by the model. Precipitation was determined from 18 meteorological stations covering the entire basin. Monthly precipitation data were defined in the model. Ordinary kriging was used to estimate the transient precipitation distribution over the entire domain. Figure 3 gives the spatial distribution of the average annual precipitation.

Soil maps and well logs of the top soil indicate that the soil is mostly silty loam. In the model, the permeability and van Genuchten parameters of the soil are defined based on soil type and direct measurements of the water retention properties of collected soil samples. Geologic maps and well logs developed by the State Hydraulics Works (Devlet Su İşleri, DSI) were used to define the hydraulic conductivity of the aquifer. The thickness of the aquifer was interpolated based on a series of well logs. Wherever the bottom of the aquifer was not

reached, the bottom elevation was defined equal to the bottom of the well logs. The initial transmissivity values used in the model ranged from 600 to 8000 m²/day.

Irrigation water demand was based on historical crop production yields (TUIK, 2020), recommended irrigation schedules for the area of Konya for different crops (TAGEM, 2017) and land use satellite maps (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service). As the number of pumping wells in the Konya basin is estimated to be around 100,000, with closed to two-thirds unregulated, it is not possible to model individual wells. Instead, groundwater extraction rates for each model grid were defined as the difference between the irrigation water demand within that grid and the actual precipitation. Potential evapotranspiration rates were defined based on climate data and land use maps on a monthly basis.

The calibration target was the historical monthly groundwater level data at various monitoring wells covering the entire model domain. The main calibration parameters were the spatial distribution of the transmissivity, as well as irrigation and groundwater extraction rates which are associated with the highest level of uncertainty.

Description of the surrogate model

The surrogate model will be developed using artificial neural network, as soon as the complete model will be delivered.

2.4. Grombalia (Tunisia)

Objectives of the surrogate model

The objective of the surrogate model developed for the Grombalia aquifer is to provide a quick tool to investigate the impact of future climate scenarios on the groundwater resources.

A complete numerical model is not available for this study area; therefore, a data-driven surrogate model has been developed based on groundwater levels, precipitation and temperature data. Assuming that the hydrological processes will not change over time, the proposed method is a statistical method that allows a fast evaluation of groundwater variations based on precipitation and temperature future scenarios.

Description of the data

The involved study area, shown in Figure 17, is the Grombalia shallow aquifer. The precipitation and temperature data were collected from six rain gauges and one temperature station in the period 1976-2020 (Figure 17 and Table 4). The precipitation data have been processed with the Thiessen polygon techniques to obtain their areal averages. Instead, the areal temperature was considered equal to that recorded in the only available station.

Figure 17. Study area and location of the temperature and rain stations and monitoring wells.

Table 3. Station name and station code of the gauging stations.

Station Name	Station code	Rain	Temp
Bezirk Dam	TUN002	X	
Beni Khaled Ferme	TUN005	X	
CTV Bouargoub	TUN006	X	
Grombalia DRE	TUN007	X	
CTV Menzel Bouzelfa	TUN008	X	
CTV Soliman	TUN009	X	
Nabeul	TUN010		X

Groundwater level data were collected from 23 wells selected for their data availability in the period 1976-2020 (Figure 17 and Table 4).

Table 4. Name and codes of the monitoring wells.

Well Name	Well code	Well Name	Well code
12440	W1	8588	W13
6922	W2	13397	W14
2183	W3	12202	W15
2171	W4	13571	W16
2543	W5	8844	W17
2534	W6	2379	W18
1404	W7	12134	W19
2008	W8	12405	W20
2025	W9	12406	W21
11419	W10	12961	W22
13474	W11	13329	W23
8589	W12		

Description of the surrogate model

A simple data-driven surrogate model has been developed to evaluate the impacts of climate change on groundwater levels (Secci et al., 2021). A linear regression model has been used to describe the relationship between meteorological variables and groundwater levels (GWL). The first step for the development of the surrogate model is to investigate if the historical rainfall and temperature data and groundwater levels collected in monitoring wells are correlated. The climate variables are investigated in terms of Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Indices (SPEIs) computed at different accumulation periods (3, 6, 9, 12, 18, 24 and 36 months). The SPEI index depends on climate variables only (Vicente-Serrano et al. 2010); it uses the monthly differences between precipitation and potential

evapotranspiration. The meteorological indices and GWL data are defined correlated if the Pearson correlation coefficient is greater than 0.7.

For those wells presenting satisfactory correlation, a linear regression relationship has been computed between GWLs and SPEIs. This linear regression model represents the surrogate model that describes the dependence of groundwater levels on meteorological variables and will be used to evaluate the future groundwater levels based on future SPEI values, estimated by means of an ensemble of regional climate models (RCMs) under different climate scenarios (RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5).

Preliminary evaluation of the performance

The correlation between the GWLs of each well and SPEIs computed at the different time scales have been initially evaluated considering all the available data and then using only GWLs observed in February, March and April. The results are depicted in Figure 18. The Pearson correlation coefficients are very low if computed on all the available data for all wells. On the contrary, correlations increase for some wells if the analysis is computed on the period February-April. This stems for the fact that groundwater resources in these months presents minimal anthropogenic influence due to pumping and irrigation. The wells that do not show correlation for both analyses are likely affected by external factors and they do not respond to the meteorological variables. Moreover, the results highlight a different sensitivity of the well data to the climate variables; the wells present the highest correlation at different time scale. The groundwater levels respond to the climate variables with different time lag probably due to the distinct characteristics of the aquifer and wells depths.

Therefore, the surrogate model has been developed based on late winter and early spring months data and considering the wells that present at least a Pearson correlation coefficient greater than 0.7, resulting in eight correlated wells.

Figure 18 - Pearson correlation coefficients between groundwater levels observed at the 23 wells (y-axis) and the and SPEIs at the time scale of 3, 6, 9, 12, 18, 24 and 36 months (x-axes) considering all months (a) and February-April months, respectively.

In Figure 19 to Figure 26, the results for all the eight correlated wells are shown; the linear regression models with their confidence interval are depicted.

For future projections (Task 3.4), the regression model calculated considering the SPEI at the time scale with the highest correlation will be used as surrogate model.

Figure 19. Linear regression model for the well 12440. The x-axis shows the SPEI values and the y-axis the groundwater level in m a.s.l. The points are the observed groundwater levels, the solid line is the regression line and the dashed lines are the confidence intervals (95%); the correlation coefficients are reported in the boxes.

Figure 20. Linear regression model for the well 2183. The x-axis shows the SPEI values and the y-axis the groundwater level in m a.s.l. The points are the observed groundwater levels, the solid line is the regression line and the dashed lines are the confidence intervals (95%); the correlation coefficients are reported in the boxes.

Figure 21. Linear regression model for the well 2171. The x-axis shows the SPEI values and the y-axis the groundwater level in m a.s.l. The points are the observed groundwater levels, the solid line is the regression line and the dashed lines are the confidence intervals (95%); the correlation coefficients are reported in the boxes.

Figure 22. Linear regression model for the well 2543. The x-axis shows the SPEI values and the y-axis the groundwater level in m a.s.l. The points are the observed groundwater levels, the solid line is the regression line and the dashed lines are the confidence intervals (95%); the correlation coefficients are reported in the boxes.

Figure 23. Linear regression model for the well 2008. The x-axis shows the SPEI values and the y-axis the groundwater level in m a.s.l. The points are the observed groundwater levels, the solid line is the regression line and the dashed lines are the confidence intervals (95%); the correlation coefficients are reported in the boxes.

Figure 24. Linear regression model for the well 8844. The x-axis shows the SPEI values and the y-axis the groundwater level in m a.s.l. The points are the observed groundwater levels, the solid line is the regression line and the dashed lines are the confidence intervals (95%); the correlation coefficients are reported in the boxes.

Figure 25. Linear regression model for the well 2379. The x-axis shows the SPEI values and the y-axis the groundwater level in m a.s.l. The points are the observed groundwater levels, the solid line is the regression line and the dashed lines are the confidence intervals (95%); the correlation coefficients are reported in the boxes.

Figure 26. Linear regression model for the well 12405. The x-axis shows the SPEI values and the y-axis the groundwater level in m a.s.l. The points are the observed groundwater levels, the solid line is the regression line and the dashed lines are the confidence intervals (95%); the correlation coefficients are reported in the boxes.

2.5. Castro Verde (Portugal)

Objectives of the surrogate model

The objectives of the surrogate model for Castro Verde (Portugal) are the investigation of potential impacts of mining activities on groundwater and the forecast of future scenarios. A complete numerical model is under development and it will be used to train a smart model.

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